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Regional decision-makers as potential users of Extreme Weather Event Attribution - Case studies from the German Baltic Sea coast and the Greater Paris area

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ABSTRACT

Extreme Event Attribution has raised increasing attention in climate science in the last years. It means to judge the extent to which certain weather-related extreme events have changed due to human influences on climate with probabilistic statements. Extreme Event Attribution is often anticipated to spur more than just scientific ambition. It is able to provide answers to a commonly asked questions after extreme events, namely, ‘can we blame it on climate change’ and is assumed to support decision-making of various actors engaged in climate change mitigation and adaptation. More in-depth research is widely lacking about who these actors are; in which context they can make use of it; and what requirements they have, to be able to actually apply Extreme Event Attribution. We have therefore addressed these questions with two empirical case studies looking at regional decision-makers who deal with storm surge risks in the German Baltic Sea region and heat waves in the Greater Paris area. Stakeholder interviews and workshops reveal that fields of application and requirements are diverse, difficult to explicitly identify, and often clearly associated with stakeholders' specific mandate, the hazard background, and the regional socio-economic setting. Among the considered stakeholders in the Baltic Sea region, Extreme Event Attribution is perceived to be most useful to awareness-raising, in particular for climate change mitigation. They emphasised the importance of receiving understandable information - and that, rather later, but with smaller uncertainties than faster, but with higher uncertainties. In the *Paris* case, we typically talked to people engaged in adaptation with expertise in terms of climate science, but narrowly defined mandates which is typical for the Paris-centred political system with highly specialised public experts. The interviewees claimed that Extreme Event Attribution is most useful to political leverage and public discourses. If novel information like this is not sorted out a priori, it needs to be clearly linked to impacts, preferably as monetary values lost. These examples underline the significance of conducting case-specific stakeholder mappings and consultation. Overall, our studies can thereby provide methods and exemplary empirical evidence to support developing useful services from Extreme Event Attribution for targeted groups of users.

1. Introduction and background

In 2007, the IPCC addressed for the first time general attribution studies, i.e. the evaluation of the relative contribution of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions to climate change. The report states that more than 50% of the observed increased global average temperatures since mid of last century are very likely to be caused by the emission of anthropogenic greenhouse gases. This trend attribution shows whether climate change is generally linked to anthropogenic greenhouse gases. Nevertheless, it does not show whether and in how far specific extreme events are attributable to anthropogenic climate change. This is a question which is often posed after extreme events, but which has rarely been answered to date (Stott et al., 2016; Hulme, 2014; James et al., 2014). The World Climate Research Programme declared that answers to this question are essential for ‘Understanding and Predicting Weather and Climate Extremes’ and identified it therefore as part of the six grand

challenges of climate research (World Climate Research Programme, 2013; Seneviratne Zwiers, 2015). In the last two decades, a range of scientists have aimed at meeting this challenge by continuously advancing the science of Extreme Event Attribution. This field of research is meant to judge the extent to which certain weather-related extreme events have changed due to human influences on climate with probabilistic statements (Hegerl et al., 2010). Extreme event attribution tries to overcome the problem of rarity regarding extreme events by simulating tens of thousands of times the occurrence of extreme weather events in two virtual worlds. One world where our atmosphere and climate is reproduced as it is today and another world which simulates a pre-industrial-like world without anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. These two worlds are then compared with each other (see e.g. Solow, 2015).

It is often argued that scientists, media, and practitioners are interested in rising to this “grand challenge” for different reasons (see e.g.

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Hulme, 2014; Hegerl et al., 2010; James et al., 2014; Sippel et al., 2015). Scientists seem to be spurred by scientific ambition to master the methodological complexities; the media hopes to answer one of the most commonly asked questions after extreme events, i.e. who is to blame for it; and decision-makers fondly hope to get justification, funding and a better knowledge base for managing climate-related risks. Overall, it seems to be anticipated that Extreme Event Attribution may make anthropogenic climate change more visible or invisible if no link is found. Negative consequences of climatic conditions in general and climate change become most apparent through extreme events. Extreme Event Attribution quantifies whether these extremes are linked to anthropogenic greenhouse gases. It does thereby not argue on an abstract level of long-term climate changes which can hardly be experienced by individuals over a lifetime. Extreme Event Attribution is able to demonstrate the imminent perils of climate change at a vivid example of recent extreme events and may reveal that climate change is or is not real already today. Research which goes beyond the understanding that Extreme Event Attribution is important for stakeholders and which empirically identifies potential groups of users or maps possible needs of different sectors, institutions and agents is still rare (Stott and Walton, 2013). Also a more detailed empirical analysis of these stakeholders' needs, for instance, against the background of context-, hazard- or region-specific factors, or with respect to their implications for climate change-related decision-making has not been undertaken, so far.

This paper therefore aims at answering the questions of who could be potential user groups at the regional level, whether their interests coincide with what is often assumed to interest them, and what requirements may exist in different fields of their work. These questions are addressed using the example of stakeholders engaged in managing the risks of climate change, storm surges at the German Baltic Sea coast, and heat waves in the Greater Paris area. We answered the above mentioned questions with a qualitative empirical case study and analysed them in light of concepts which link science and practice. This has revealed that it is important to be aware of the mandate, background and needs of different stakeholder groups. It became apparent that there is not one set of potential users, but that they are different depending on the region and hazard under consideration. In the test cases, we found that Extreme Event Attribution products should be understandable, trustworthy, and tailored to stakeholders' specific concerns. In the end, this study shall provide a basis to effectively communicate and frame attribution studies and create useful services from Extreme Event Attribution.

In this paper, a literature review about Extreme Event Attribution research and its relevance to stakeholders will be presented first. Subsequently, we will introduce the materials, methods and concepts used in the two case studies. The results will be outlined and discussed in the next section. In the end, general conclusions will be drawn.

2. Existing research on Extreme Event Attribution and its assumed relevance to stakeholders

Extreme Event Attribution information may serve an already long-lasting public interest in the so called 'extreme weather blame' question, i.e. who is responsible for extreme weather. He further states that in the past, this question has commonly been answered by blaming god, evil spirits or witches (Hulme, 2014). In recent decades, man-made greenhouse gas emissions are often made responsible for extreme weather events. Several authors therefore argue that Extreme Event Attribution information could increase scientific rigour in the debate and add probabilities to such assumptions. In addition, it could ease the frustration with and the argument about the invisibility of climate change because extreme events are more visible than creeping climate changes (Stott and Walton, 2013; Sippel et al., 2015; Bray and von Storch, 2016).

There is a growing number of studies which have judged the contribution of climate change to particular events. These are based on various methodologies and models (for an extensive overview of Extreme Event Attribution approaches see Stott et al., 2016). Some of the studies found

that climate change is responsible for the intensity and frequency of extreme events considered, e.g. in case of the heat wave in Europe in 2003 (Stott et al., 2004a,b), the floods in the UK in autumn 2000 (Pall et al., 2011), the cold spell in the US (Wolter et al., 2015); others detected no significant anthropogenic influence on climate, like in case of Storm Christian in 2013 (von Storch et al., 2014) and Hurricane Gonzalo (Feser et al., 2015). For the latter, there have, however, also been contradictory results presented indicating an anthropogenic contribution (Rahmstorf and Coumou, 2011).

Since 2011, yearly collections of attribution studies of events from the previous calendar year have been published as Special Issue of the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS). An analysis of all events assessed in the 2011–2014 BAMS reports shows that most BAMS studies have looked at heat, precipitation and drought. Storm surges or winter storms have been assessed only once. These reports present case studies of event attribution of the recent past (Herring, 2015). They support the visibility of attribution studies also beyond the scientific community. More recently, event attribution scholars have further demonstrated that Extreme Event Attribution can be done in near-real time (see e.g. van Oldenborgh et al., 2015; van Oldenborgh et al., 2016). Climate Central, a non-profit environmental news organization, has published a near real-time example of "weather attribution" in July 2015. Building on weather forecasts and later on the observed temperatures during the July 2015 heat wave in Europe, they found that, for example, a 3-day period as hot as experienced in Mannheim is now roughly 8 times more likely than it was in the 1930s. This was published only a couple of days after the event (Climate Central, 2015). Attribution scientists predict that within a decade from now attribution methods may become an operational product like local weather forecasts (Stott et al., 2016; Zastrow, 2015). Extreme Event Attribution studies have, however, been criticised for having a too hazard-centred view on risk (see e.g. Hulme, 2014). They only look at the causes of hazard changes, but do not look at what drives vulnerabilities and exposure. Challenging this critique, there are already some examples of event attribution studies which link the meteorological causation to infrastructure, ecosystem, or hydrological analyses (see e.g. Pall et al., 2011; Sippel and Otto, 2014; Mitchell et al., 2016; Schaller et al., 2016).

Despite of these advances, many stakeholders and the public seem to think that it is not possible to attribute a single event to anthropogenic climate change (Hegerl et al., 2010; Thompson and Otto, 2015). Bray and von Storch (2016) reveal that many scientists share this opinion. In their survey of climate scientists, nearly one third believes that Extreme Event Attribution efforts have not provided robust evidence of attributing events to climate change at all or only to a minor degree (Bray and von Storch, 2016: 83). Extreme weather can be generated by natural variability also without climate change. Another point of criticism, in this respect, is that extreme events are too rare to attribute a single event to climate change. Extreme Event Attribution, however, builds on ensembles of simulations of climate models and can therefore overcome this challenge (IDAG, 2005; James et al., 2014).

There is a key argument which can hardly be overcome and limits the confidence in event attribution results. This is the assumption that a given climate model, or a given family of climate models, is really describing the full range of phenomena in terms of intensity and frequency. In many cases, this may be the case, but in others the contemporary models will have their limitations. One case refers to a model-setup used in event attribution and its performance in simulating weather conditions which lead to storm surges in the Baltic Sea (Klehmet et al., 2016). Thus, when scientists speak about changing probabilities, they talk about estimates of probabilities which may, in fact, be systematically over- or underestimated; and different models may generate different statistics of extreme events and their change. Accordingly, the confidence in the event attribution depends critically on the confidence of the used models to generate extreme events correctly in terms of the locations, seasonal timing, frequency, intensity etc. (von Storch, and Bray, 2017).

Some authors argue that Extreme Event Attribution statements

confuse the public and decision-makers (Hulme, 2014; James et al., 2014). It may reduce rather than increase the trust in science and anthropogenic climate change. It is argued that the probabilistic statements are loaded with uncertainties and the public often associates uncertainties with opposing scientific views about the feasibility and results of Extreme Event Attribution. Moreover, some stakeholders argue that scientists' lack of capability to communicate complex statements is a major concern which might inhibit the application of Extreme Event Attribution information as has been argued in a panel discussion conducted by Stott and Walton (2013). Event Attribution sceptics also state that climate models are not able to reproduce the complexity and dynamics attached to extreme weather events. This is yet a problem which is not specific to Extreme Event Attribution, but a general problem of model experiments to predict future climate. Decision-makers have to accept that Extreme Event Attribution will not provide certainty - an aspect which they routinely deal with in case of climate projections already today. In fact, the most that Extreme Event Attribution is meant to provide are probabilities. In Adam's (2011) words, greenhouse gas emissions "load the dice" and can make some weather events more likely - Extreme Event Attribution will tell you by how much these events are more likely - under the assumption that the "real dice" is faithfully reproduced by the "models' dice".

In order to understand stakeholder needs and requirements in terms of Extreme Event Attribution, potential user groups have to be identified. Stott et al. (2013) identify four major groups of Extreme Event Attribution users based on their experiences from previous Extreme Event Attribution studies. These are: the general public, the legal sector, adaptation planning, and the geo-engineering sector. Other authors further identify the insurance sector, agriculture, health sector, and the media as potential users of Extreme Event Attribution information (Hulme, 2014; James et al., 2014; Sippel et al., 2015; Stott and Walton, 2013). With respect to adaptation planning, for instance, Extreme Event Attribution results could indicate that a specific event is and will be extremely rare. It should therefore not be prioritized in the adaptation agenda (Stott and Walton, 2013). Extreme Event Attribution might, on the other hand, also show that a specific extreme event is a signifier of the future to which society should better adapt. In this case, Extreme Event Attribution information would not only enhance the justification for taking action and facilitate more effective resource distribution, but would also improve planning and implementation of climate adaptation (Stott et al., 2013; Stott and Walton, 2013). The survey of Bray and von Storch (2016) shows that this view seems to be shared by many scientists who believe that Extreme Event Attribution can improve the planning and execution of climate adaptation strategies. Hulme and his co-authors (2011) criticize in this context that Extreme Event Attribution information might allocate adaptation funds to places where hazards are most attributable to anthropogenic climate change and not to where people are most vulnerable to meteorological hazards. Moreover, information about the causes of the hazard per se does not facilitate more appropriate adaptation planning. They find that the large uncertainties attached to Extreme Event Attribution results increase the complexity of the adaptation debate, support climate sceptics and re-open debates about unresolved uncertainties which had already occurred in the past rather than enhancing the argument for taking adaptation actions (Hulme et al., 2011).

The identification of the above mentioned sectors mainly builds upon Extreme Event Attribution studies which have been undertaken so far, in particular on studies about the contribution of anthropogenic climate change to extreme events like heat waves, cold spells, heavy rainfall or flooding - mainly in the UK and the US. The identification of potential stakeholders has not been sufficiently reflected against the background of context-, hazard-, or region-specific factors. To shed light on such aspects, we analyse at regional stakeholders in two test cases in different regions, with a different hazard context, and different sectors affected.

3. Methods and concepts

Conducting an empirical study is essential for understanding potential stakeholder needs and requirements in terms of Extreme Event Attribution. In this paper, we want to test if our case study reflects the argumentation presented in the literature review above. A focus will hereby lie on the identification of potential users, the relevance and potential benefits and disadvantages of Extreme Event Attribution for them, and criteria which determine the utility of Extreme Event Attribution for stakeholders. This is done against the background of literature about utility assessments of science for practitioners. The following section will briefly elaborate on ways of doing this and setting grounds for describing the methods used for this study.

To understand whether, why and in how far Extreme Event Attribution information is useful for stakeholders' decision-making, we decided for a flexible qualitative approach engaging two main methods of data collection, i.e. qualitative interviews and participatory stakeholder workshops (see e.g. Kruker and Rauh, 2005, Kitzinger, 1995, Flick, 2007, Breitenfelder et al., 2004 for more details about the advantages and caveats of qualitative research). Our research focuses on stakeholders concerned with climate change on the one hand and, on the other hand, storm surges at the German Baltic Sea coast and heat waves in the greater Paris area.

In the *German Baltic Sea region*, storm surges are a risk to people, infrastructure, and landscape. They are, nevertheless, often not perceived as such by regional stakeholders directly or indirectly in charge of dealing with storm surges from e.g. city administrations, private sector, or civil society (see e.g. Koerth and Sterr, 2012). This is likely to be caused by the fact that storm surge events with extreme consequences, such as in 1872 (Bork and Müller-Navarra, 2009) or 1913 (von Storch et al., 2014; Wagner et al., 2016), have not happened in recent decades. Taking a scenario of a storm surge like in 1872, many actors and institutions seem not sufficiently prepared, also today (see e.g. Schröder, 2013; Koerth and Sterr, 2012; UBA, 2012).

In the greater Paris area, the traumatic scale of the 2003 heat wave with a 75–100% excess mortality (INVS, 2003) has left profound effects in the organization of emergency response and in the management of heat waves (Ledrans, 2006). An increase in intensity and frequency of heat waves is seen as a central threat associated with climate change for the Greater Paris area. Public health agency and structure dealing with adaptation to climate change identify heat waves as a central component of their activities. Most of the interviewees are engaged in adaptation¹ and have a high level of expertise in climate change and impact. This is typical to the French policymaking culture with a centralized and extremely segmented nature of French governmental organization. These characteristics are reinforced by the fact that Paris is the national capital and concentrates human resources and expertise.

The research is able to exemplarily reveal the relevance of 'context' in an analysis of potential stakeholder interests by making use of case studies of different regions and socio-political contexts (German Baltic Sea Coast and Greater Paris area), hazards (storm surges and heat waves), and sectors (e.g. coastal protection and health planning). The stakeholders were selected based on an internet-based research, on the one hand, and on the other hand, according to snowball sampling, meaning that interviewed people referred us to other decision-makers relevant to our research. The sample was intended to include a broad variety of representatives of different institutional and sectorial foci (see Table 1). The stakeholders are engaged in climate change adaptation, mitigation,² or storm surge/heat wave risk management in the selected regions. They are engaged in civil society organisations, in ministries, in authorities and

¹ Adaptation refers here and in the following to adaptation to possible consequences of future climate change. Impact mitigation is an alternatively used term for adaptation.

² Mitigation refers here and in the following to a reduction of the causes of climate change by reducing greenhouse gases.

Table 1
Sectorial foci of the interviewed stakeholders.

<i>German Baltic Sea case study</i>	<i>Paris case study</i>		
Sectorial foci of the interviewed stakeholders	No. of interviews conducted	Sectorial foci of the interviewed stakeholders	No. of interviews conducted
emergency management	1	health care, health planning, mass transit, collective provision of temperature regulation (cold).	0
spatial planning	2	urban planning,	1
tourism	1	local and regional climate planning, regional climate office	5
nature protection	1	Rural planning agriculture	1
climate change mitigation	2		
coastal protection	1		
maritime/port industry	1		
Total:	9 interviews	Total:	7 interviews

administrations, in associations, in education institutions, and in the private sector.

The selection of the sectorial and contextual foci in each of the regional cases was developed according to the following criteria: significant exposure to the respective extreme event and climate change-related impacts; evident need for regional climate information given current socio-economic problems with respect to the hazard; evinced interest of stakeholder groups in regional climate services. The interviewees were selected based on two main criteria: their experience and role as regional decision-makers as well as extensive networking with other regional stakeholders. The latter facilitated a snowball sampling, i.e. a sampling “through referrals made among people who share or know of others who possess some characteristics that are of research interest” [Birnacki und Waldorf 1981, p. 141].

The interviews were conducted in an open and flexible way with little interference from the interviewer. They lasted between 30 min and 2 h and were conducted face to face. The interviews addressed the following questions: How do regional stakeholders understand Extreme Event Attribution? How do they perceive the usefulness of regional climate services in general and Extreme Event Attribution information in particular? What makes a regional climate and potential Extreme Event Attribution service relevant, reliable and expedient for stakeholders and related decisions?

The focus group workshops were facilitated by the researchers and followed principles of qualitative and participatory approaches. They started with presentations to outline the overall context of climate change, extreme events and Extreme Event Attribution. These were followed by two group sessions: 1) Regional climate services – how to transform scientific results into credible, legitimate and relevant information products? and 2) Quantifying the contribution of anthropogenic climate change to storm surges/heat wave events as an example for ‘good’ regional climate services. These were followed by a results gallery where outcomes of the sessions were summarised and presented. The workshop lasted one afternoon for the Baltic Sea group and one day in the Paris case study. In total, nine interviews and one workshop were conducted in the German Baltic Sea region and seven interviews and two workshops in the Greater Paris area.

To assess the relevance, potential benefits and disadvantages of information from Extreme Event Attribution science for different stakeholder groups, the data was analysed against the background of concepts about the usefulness of science for practitioners, in particular on Cash et al. (2002, 2003). They argue that science-based information is most likely to feed into decision-making for sustainable development if the boundaries between knowledge and action are managed in ways “that simultaneously enhance [their] salience, credibility, and legitimacy [...]” (Cash et al., 2003). Salience refers to “the relevance of information for an actor’s decision choices, or for the choices that affect a given stakeholder” (Cash et al., 2002: 4); credibility involves, according to Cash et al. (2003: 8086), “the scientific adequacy of the technical evidence and arguments”; legitimacy reflects, according to Cash et al. (2003: 8086), that research has considered stakeholders’ needs and interests. This is often

based on the judgment of who participated in what way in knowledge production, assessment and dissemination. To grasp how to fulfil these requirements we also draw von Storch et al. (2011) who claim that it is essential to assess and understand regional experiences, memories and values; present information in an understandable manner, consider relevant region-specific impacts, and embed scientific findings in the overall political and societal decision-making context. Pielke (2007) argues that a responsible scientist should function as an “honest broker” meaning that he/she should understand complex processes and research results and communicate them without advocating personal preferences. This shall help identifying expedient ‘solutions’ even if uncertainties are high.

4. Results and discussion

Similar to what other studies assume (see e.g. Hegerl et al., 2010; Thompson and Otto, 2015), all interviewed stakeholders were, on enquiry, sceptical that Extreme Event Attribution is actually possible or is able to produce reliable results. Methodological details, such as the selection of appropriate climate models or event attribution approaches, as well as potential results have been perceived to be rather abstract and complex. Stakeholders who are not expert in climate science (the majority of regional stakeholders) misunderstood Extreme Event Attribution in several cases. Some said, for instance, that they understand what Extreme Event Attribution is about, but referred to it as information equivalent to scenarios of future extreme events further on in the interview or discussion.

This was in particular so in the case of the Baltic Sea region, where the stakeholders were neither expert in climate science, nor familiar with Extreme Event Attribution. Moreover, Extreme Event Attribution studies about Baltic Sea storm surges did not exist at the time of the interviews. In addition, an appropriate term for Extreme Event Attribution in German language does not exist. This made it even more complicated to convey an understanding of Extreme Event Attribution (see also Vanderlinden et al., 2015). Being unacquainted with the concept of Extreme Event Attribution and the lack of exemplary studies of Extreme Event Attribution about Baltic Sea storm surges made it also difficult for the consulted stakeholders to identify potential fields of application and express specific and concrete requirements regarding Extreme Event Attribution information or services. A workshop participant from a federal state authority for coastal protection in Northern Germany expressed this as follows: “[...] *the things that I don't know, these are also the things that I cannot ask for. This is the difficulty in this respect*”.

In the Paris case study, in contrast, the interviewees and workshop participants were all ‘climate change reference persons’ within the various sectors that we targeted and were therefore better able to deal with a complex scientific field such as Extreme Event Attribution. Moreover, heat waves have, in contrast to storm surges, already been probabilistically attributed to climate change. This may have made this field of research more concrete and accessible for the interviewed stakeholders.

The empirical results of both case studies show that there is a general interest in Extreme Event Attribution, but that it is not directly relevant to their work. An employee of a private consulting firm for spatial planning in the context of extreme events in the German Baltic Sea region said:

“ [Extreme Event Attribution is interesting] as general information, but [...] I currently do not see where it would support our daily work; because we care more about the practical management of impacts or warnings regarding extreme events [rather than explaining the causes]”.

Several stakeholders argue in this context that there is no real added value from Extreme Event Attribution results. The head of an initiative to raise awareness for more climate mitigation in the *German Baltic Sea* case study explained it as follows:

„If [climate change contributes to this extreme event] now by 60% or 90% - this is something one can sublimely conduct research about – for me, it is enough to know that humans are responsible to a substantial degree and this is more of an ethical question [...]”

When asking the consulted stakeholders whether they think that Extreme Event Attribution information would be of use to other fields of work, all of them answered that it might be better able to influence decision-making of other stakeholders than their own. In the literature, it is argued that the need for Extreme Event Attribution is particularly evident for litigations, actors engaged in climate change adaptation, and decision-makers concerned with geo-engineering (see e.g. [Stott et al., 2013](#); [Sippel et al., 2015](#)). We asked the considered stakeholders whether they know any sectors or fields of work which could benefit from Extreme Event Attribution information and why that is the case. The above mentioned sectors were rarely or not at all identified to be potential users of Extreme Event Attribution information by the regional stakeholders selected for the two case studies (see [Table 2](#)). Litigations like in the US or at the international scale (see e.g. [Adam, 2011](#); [Faulk, 2012](#); [Stott and Walton, 2013](#)) have not fed into the general societal and technical debate about climate change in Germany or France – particularly not at the regional scale. Geo-engineering might not have been named by stakeholders in the case studies because none of the stakeholders was directly or indirectly concerned with it. It is a topic which is debated at the national if not international scale rather than by regional decision-makers -

Table 2

Stakeholder groups and fields where Extreme Event Attribution could be needed according to interviewees and workshop participants (Source: key stakeholder interviews, workshop discussion).

Storm Surges in the Baltic Sea		Heat waves in the Greater Paris area	
Potential fields of application	mentioned	Potential fields of application	mentioned
Climate change mitigation	Frequently	Societal/Public CC discourse	Frequently
Public CC discourse		Public awareness-raising	
Public awareness-raising		Political leverage	
Politics		Internal awareness raising	
Insurances	Few times	Insurances	Few times
Compensation mechanisms		Basis for better scenarios	
Civic participation	Rarely	Compensation mechanisms	Never
Political leverage		Administration	
Administration		Universities	
Universities		Civic participation	
Basis for better scenarios		General education	
General education		Climate change mitigation	
Coastal protection		Spatial planning	
Spatial planning		Geo-engineering	
Internal awareness raising		Litigation	
Geo-engineering	Never		
Litigation			

which were at the centre of this study. This indicates that not only the profession of the stakeholders shapes the way how they perceive their and other people's needs in terms of Extreme Event Attribution, but also the geographic and socio-political context in which they act.

Climate change mitigation was a commonly identified potential user of Extreme Event Attribution in the *Baltic Sea* case study (not in the *Paris* case, though; see [Table 2](#)). In this context, knowing about the causes and not only impacts of changes in extreme events can provide motivation to act. The relevance of Extreme Event Attribution-based information was perceived to be more an issue to the general societal debate about climate change, political lobbying, and awareness-raising activities. This was generally more linked to mitigation than to adaptation because Extreme Event Attribution deals with greenhouse gas emissions as a source of climate change. Mitigation is meant to counteract this cause; Adaptation is meant to counteract the consequences of climate change (adaptation will be discussed later in this section). An urban planner in a city administration at the German Baltic Sea coast explains it as follows:

„[...] If there is someone who provides solid prove that certain climatological phenomena are man-made – if this would show me that I have to better accept the existing more or less threatening projections – then related actions which try to counteract the problem would become more plausible to me. [...] If I assume that everything is the way it is, anyway, and it does not have anything to do with me, why should I then deal with climate mitigation [...]?”

Moreover, it seemed important to some of the stakeholders interested in raising the awareness in terms of climate change-related threats that the kind of results produced by Extreme Event Attribution point into the ‘right’ direction. They accordingly indicated that Extreme Event Attribution results should not be communicated if they do not indicate a significant contribution of anthropogenic climate change. To increase the usefulness of Extreme Event Attribution for stakeholders concerned with public awareness-raising, it was further emphasised that results should be linked to the specific problems and to the regional consequences of extreme events.

Political leverage and internal awareness-raising were frequently mentioned fields of application by the consulted stakeholders in the *Paris* case. Here, the considered climate change reference persons have relatively narrowly defined mandates generally centred on operational matters associated with adaptation to climate change. Information about the causes of impacts were therefore most relevant, meaning more things like increased exposure, vulnerabilities or risk management capacities than causes of hazard changes. Linking Extreme Event Attribution to impacts is, however, rarely undertaken as the previous literature review reveals. Extreme Event Attribution information is therefore likely to be sorted out if stakeholders do not see the direct relevance of the information to their work. An interviewee in the *Paris* test case argues along these lines:

“Sometimes it's not really an extreme event, it is rather extreme conditions for what infrastructures are designed to withstand”

Linking, for example, probabilistic Extreme Event Attribution statements to losses and damages which occurred due to an extreme event were perceived to be more relevant than without, like these stakeholders concerned with heat wave risks in *Paris* describe:

“If we want to make a qualitative leap we must work on the data interface to characterize a potential increase in storms associated to this level costs, otherwise we cannot convince elected officials”.

“Data that legitimize action is data which makes intelligible impacts. The universal language today is Euro”.

This enforces the critique that Extreme Event Attribution is still too much centred on a mere hazard perspective and should rather be part of more integrative statements linked to impacts, vulnerabilities and

exposure (see e.g. Hulme et al., 2011).

Out of the three sectors suggested by Stott et al. (2013), in fact, only climate change adaptation was mentioned by some of the consulted stakeholders. In the case of *Baltic Sea* storm surges, stakeholders found that adapting large infrastructures might benefit from Extreme Event Attribution-based information. A representative of the federal state authority for coastal protection in Northern Germany, i.e. a stakeholder dealing with the regulations and planning of large infrastructures, however, did not perceive to have a major benefit of information like from Extreme Event Attribution. Stott et al. (2013) argue, in this context, that Extreme Event Attribution might facilitate a more effective resource distribution and would improve planning and implementation of climate adaptation. Several stakeholders consulted in the *Baltic Sea* case study like the representative of the federal state authority for coastal protection, however, argued to the contrary saying that they need to know *how* extreme events occur and change, rather than knowing *why* extreme events change in order to be able to improve adaptation planning. Furthermore, it is perceived to be more important to understand the underlying causes of vulnerabilities than of the hazard – as has been mentioned also in the context of political leverage in the *Paris* case. A spatial planner in the *Baltic Sea* region claims in this regard:

“Well, I think that this [Extreme Event Attribution] would not be relevant to my work, i.e. who is responsible for the heavy rainfall for instance. It is simply a fact and we have to see how to deal with the mass of water. Alright, we could of course influence the small scale regional water balance with spatial planning. And then [...] if something goes wrong, it is of course man-made. But this is then not due to the contribution of CO₂ or climate change, but simply because of sealing, heatwaves were caused in the city, or something like that; urban climate influenced by inapt planning [...]”.

If there would be fields of application for Extreme Event Attribution related to climate change adaptation, planners of large infrastructures in the *Baltic Sea* case stressed that they need certain information with one concrete value rather than results depicting large margins (e.g. worst-case water levels with a margin between 1.5 and 2.5 m) – which is to date often the case for Extreme Event Attribution. For emergency management and coastal protection, it was also mentioned that they need extreme values, like worst-case scenarios, to be better able to plan for the future. Extreme Event Attribution studies may cater this need by revealing that formerly defined worst-case scenarios may not be as rare as the ones thought of before the latest event.

Other stakeholders, particularly in the *Baltic Sea* case study, follow a similar line of argumentation as Hulme et al. (2011), i.e. that highly uncertain scientific Extreme Event Attribution results rather diminish the credibility of information from climate science and therefore weaken the argumentative basis for climate adaptation than strengthening it. Stakeholders have often encountered the problems of communicating uncertain climate change-related projections, particularly in case of storm surges, so that they were hesitant towards information which may be associated to even higher uncertainties. This following quote from a discussion about uncertainty of climate information of a stakeholder from a city administration in the *Baltic Sea* case study who deals, amongst others, with climate adaptation illustrates that regional stakeholders may be concerned that Extreme Event Attribution results therefore rather strengthen climate scepticism:

“I would even be afraid that we would do us a disservice. It is difficult enough to argue that climate change is anthropogenic. People believe this today, thank god, and it is well proven by science. And instead of making use of these quite solid results for changing the minds of politicians, we would go kind of one experiment further, now trying, speculating even more”.

Overall, it became evident that many stakeholders in both case studies have a rather low tolerance regarding uncertainties. An interviewee in the *Paris* case study describes it as follows:

“Today we have a culture centered on figures, if I tell you that things will increase by 50 with 50% of uncertainty, elected officials will tell you that your data is useless”.

The small tolerance to uncertainties does, however, not mean that a suitable Extreme Event Attribution-based product should not designate the inherent uncertainties. To the contrary, stakeholders in both case studies appreciated transparency with respect to uncertainties and the underlying methodologies to be able to work with the given information.

Generally, stakeholders particularly in the *Baltic Sea* case are mainly concerned with long-term preparedness or continuous awareness-raising campaigns. The consulted stakeholders did therefore not attach larger relevance to aspects like the time of availability. An interviewee from a civil society organization engaged in awareness-raising explains this as follows:

“An extreme event stays in people's mind for a long period of time; if you take New Orleans for instance [...]. It was so present in the media; people will remember it also two years after the event”.

In the reviewed Extreme Event Attribution literature which deals with stakeholder needs, the time of availability is named as essential criterion determining the salience of Extreme Event Attribution for potential users. This is why large efforts are currently put into developing an operational near-real time Extreme Event Attribution service (see e.g. Climate Central, 2015). For the considered stakeholders in our test cases, in contrast, a suitable product of Extreme Event Attribution should rather produce information at a later time, but with smaller uncertainties than fast, but with high uncertainties.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the reflection and comparison of the empirical results from two case studies against the background of the existing literature provides answers to the question for whom Extreme Event Attribution could be of use and why that is the case (or why not). Our research only presents results from two specific case studies with a relatively small sample of stakeholders and can therefore not provide a basis for extrapolating to the general utility of Extreme Event Attribution for regional stakeholders. Nevertheless, it provides in depth insights into key aspects to be considered and methods to appraise them. Our study highlights that it is not possible to compile *one* generic stakeholder typology of Extreme Event Attribution users. It has been shown that stakeholders concerned with storm surges in the German *Baltic Sea* region identify quite different needs and fields of application than those potentially interested in Extreme Event Attribution for heat waves in the Greater Paris area or for flooding in the UK (see e.g. Stott et al., 2013). In the German *Baltic Sea* region, climate change mitigation was perceived to be the most important field of application, while this field has not been mentioned at all in the *Paris* case study. Geo-engineering or litigation which are identified to be potential users of Extreme Event Attribution in the literature (see e.g. Adam, 2011; Faulk, 2012; Stott et al., 2013; Stott and Walton, 2013) have not been named at all in both case studies. Other fields of application such as its relevance to the public climate change discourse have been identified in the literature and in both our case studies. This exemplarily shows that important to conduct case-specific stakeholder mappings and reflect the results against the background of context-, hazard-, or region-specific factors.

Our results further indicate that a suitable product of Extreme Event Attribution for stakeholders should be explicit with respect to what Extreme Event Attribution is, mention how it is different from related concepts and methods, and explain these aspects in an understandable way. This cannot be done in the same way for all stakeholders and irrespective of time and place. It needs to be, for instance, known which aspects or methodologies require in-depth technical description, context-specific examples, or rather intuitive explanations and transparent communication of uncertainties. This demands for a regular and context-

specific stakeholder consultation which accounts, amongst other things, for the level of experience or expertise with respect to Extreme Event Attribution. If stakeholders are, for instance, not acquainted with such information at all, it is important to assess not only the need and requirements with respect to Extreme Event Attribution information, but with respect to climate and extreme event information services in general. Only in that way, is it possible to make implicit expectations explicit for a rather abstract science-based information product which has not been used before.

Our empirical case studies further show that the considered stakeholders want credible Extreme Event Attribution-based products tailored to their specific concerns. They thereby request that they need someone translating scientific information into salient and credible information. This seems to be of particular importance to stakeholders which are not engaged in activities related to climate science themselves, like in the *Baltic Sea* case and lack time and expertise to deal with complex information from Extreme Event Attribution. These are requirements which cannot be met by science alone. It demands for an understanding of stakeholder needs from scientists and an understanding from the side of stakeholders in terms of what science can/should provide. Climate services, for instance, are at the interface between science and stakeholders. They can therefore provide a basis for a much needed mutual understanding by facilitating a continuous dialogue.

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